

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON TRIBOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF AL2024 AND AL2024+PBSN COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a comparative analysis of the tribological properties of Al2024 alloy and Al2024 alloy reinforced with PbSn. Al2024, an aluminum alloy known for its high strength and fatigue resistance, is widely used in aerospace and automotive industries. The addition of PbSn aims to enhance the wear resistance and frictional behavior of Al2024, potentially extending its applications and improving its performance under demanding conditions. This study examines the tribological performance of the self-healing Al2024+PbSn alloy compared to pure Al2024. Results show that the self-healing alloy exhibits higher friction and wear. Friction decreases with increasing load but rises with speed, while wear escalates with both load and speed increases. Sliding distance significantly affects the coefficient of friction for the self-healing alloy. Using the Taguchi method, the wear performance under dry sliding conditions was analyzed, highlighting the influence of load, speed, and sliding distance. Regression analysis reveals that load and sliding distance are critical, contributing 42% and 43% to wear, respectively, for solder-filled Al2024 samples. Speed also impacts wear, contributing 23.6% for pure Al2024 and 17.5% for Al2024+PbSn samples.

Key words: Al2024, PBSN, Tribology, Wear, Friction

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the past two decades, aluminium matrix composites (AMCs) have become highly promising materials due to their exceptional properties, such as superior wear resistance, high strength, fatigue resistance, thermal conductivity, and hardness. These attributes make AMCs ideal for various applications in aerospace (e.g., satellite struts), automotive (e.g., drive shafts, brake discs), marine (e.g., yacht fittings), and defense (e.g., electronic instrument racks).

Aluminium matrix composites (AMMCs) are characterized by their low density, high specific stiffness and strength, controlled coefficient of thermal expansion, increased fatigue resistance, and superior dimensional stability at elevated temperatures. AMMCs offer engineers the ability to tailor material properties to meet specific needs. The mechanical and tribological properties of the matrix material can be significantly enhanced by incorporating a range of reinforcements, from soft materials like graphite and talc to hard ceramic particulates such as SiCp and Al_2O_3 .

Recent advancements in particulate-reinforced aluminum alloy composites have demonstrated significant improvements in tribological properties, including sliding wear, abrasive wear, friction, and seizure resistance. Sannino et al. provided an extensive review on the dry sliding wear of discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites, identifying key tribological parameters influencing friction and wear performance. These parameters include sliding velocity, normal load, volume fraction, type, and size of reinforcement. Among these, the volume fraction of reinforcement has the most substantial impact on wear resistance.

Numerous studies have explored enhancing the wear resistance of metal matrix composites (MMCs) through various types of reinforcements, consistently finding that reinforcements improve resistance to sliding wear. However, research on the dry sliding wear of aluminum alloys with PbSn particles remains limited. Therefore, this investigation focuses on examining the sliding wear behavior of Al2024 and Al2024+PbSn composites under different operating conditions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Wear is the process of removal of material from one or both of the two solid surfaces in solid state contact. It is a surface removal phenomenon and occurs mostly at outer surfaces. It is more appropriate and economical to make surface modification of existing alloys than using the wear resistant alloys.

Dry sliding wear tests for different number of specimens was conducted by using a pin-on-disc apparatus. Details of apparatus pin material Al2024 + PbSn, Disc material – EN31 Steel, Pin dimension- cylinder 25mm dia, height 25 mm, wear track dia- 120 mm.

Fig. 1 Tribo tester

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tribological characterizations were conducted to examine how operating parameters affect the friction and wear behavior of the newly developed self-healing material. The study focused on the tribo-performance characteristics, specifically contact friction and wear, of the self-healing Al2024 alloy reinforced with solder material in comparison to pure Al2024. To evaluate and compare performance, experiments were carried out on specimens both with and without the solder alloy.

3.1. Wear test

Dry sliding wear experiments were conducted for Al2024 and Al2024+PbSn under different loads, different speeds and sliding distances. The mechanisms and behavior of wear under different examining conditions were assessed. The sliding temperature was maintained constant at room temperature during the duration of the tests (60mins). The subsequent sections provide a detailed presentation of the experiments' findings.

3.1.1. Wear test for Al2024

A wear test for Al2024 involves evaluating the material's resistance to wear under various conditions. Al2024 is a high-strength aluminum alloy commonly used in aerospace and structural applications due to its excellent mechanical properties.

The wear of Al2024 is mainly influenced by the applied load during testing, as shown in Figure 2, which details volume losses at different speeds (300, 600, 900 RPM) and sliding distances (1000, 1500, 2000 m). Increased load leads to higher contact pressure and frictional heat, causing more significant wear. At 300 RPM, wear is low across all loads and distances, but it increases moderately at 600 RPM (15.67% higher) and peaks at 900 RPM (4.48 mm³ average). Shorter sliding distances result in lower wear, while longer distances (2000 m) cause the highest wear due to prolonged contact. To minimize wear, lower loads, speeds, and sliding distances are recommended, but practical applications require balancing performance and wear resistance. This study aids in optimizing operating conditions for Al2024's durability and performance.

Fig. 2 Wear behavior of pure Al2024 pins

Fig. 3 Surfaces of used test specimens of (a) Al2024 pin, (b) SEM image after wear and (c) Disk after wear at 50N, 900 RPM and 2000m sliding distance

3.1.2. Wear test for Al2024+PbSn

Evaluating the wear resistance of Al2024+PbSn involves testing volume loss under different loads, speeds, and sliding distances. Figure 4 shows that volume loss increases with higher loads due to greater contact pressure and frictional heat, leading to plastic deformation and sub-surface cracking. At 300 RPM, wear loss is low; at 600 RPM, it increases by 19.1%; and at 900 RPM, it is highest (6.97 mm³ on average). Shorter sliding distances result in lower wear loss, while longer distances (2000 m) cause the highest wear due to prolonged contact. To minimize wear, lower loads, speeds, and sliding distances are recommended, though practical applications require balancing performance and wear resistance. The study highlights the significant influence of load, speed, and distance on wear behavior, aiding in optimizing operating conditions for Al2024+PbSn.

Fig. 4 Wear behaviour of Al2024+PbSn pins

Fig. 5 Surfaces of used test specimens of (a) Al2024 pin, (b) SEM image after wear and (c) Disk after wear at 50N, 900 RPM and 2000m sliding distance

3.2. Friction test

The contact friction between the dry sliding of pin and disc has been measured. To benchmark the friction behavior, experiments were conducted using pure Al2024 pins. The impact of operating conditions on contact friction has been analyzed. Following this, the friction behavior of self-healing Al2024 pins reinforced with solder alloy was examined. The effects of operating parameters, including applied load, speed, and sliding distance, were discussed.

3.2.1. Friction behavior of pure Al2024

Figure 6 illustrates the coefficient of friction (CoF) of Al2024 alloy under varying speeds and sliding distances as a function of applied loads. The CoF decreases with increasing load due to the formation of an oxide layer at higher temperatures, which reduces direct surface contact. At 300 RPM, the CoF is higher across all loads and sliding distances due to more adhesive interactions. The CoF averages at different speeds (300, 600, 900 RPM) and sliding distances (1000, 1500, 2000 m) are 0.27, 0.31, and 0.32; 0.27, 0.33, and 0.37; and 0.31, 0.38, and 0.41, respectively. Higher sliding velocity and distance lead to an increase in CoF due to higher frictional force and temperature. The CoF is influenced by the mechanical properties of the matrix material, reinforcement particles' hardness and chemical stability, matrix-reinforcement interfacial strength, and tribological parameters.

Fig. 6 Influence of load on coefficient of friction of Al2024 varying the speed and sliding distance

3.2.2. Friction behavior of Al2024+PbSn

Figure 7 illustrates the friction behavior of the Al2024+PbSn composite, showing that friction decreases with increasing load but increases with higher speeds. The CoF for Al6061 filled with solder is 0.37, 0.27, and 0.17 for 10N, 30N, and 50N, respectively, at 300 RPM and a 1000m sliding distance. As speed increases, the CoF rises, with values of 0.27, 0.32, and 0.34 at 300, 600, and 900 RPM, respectively. Higher speeds generate more frictional force, causing asperities to form a lubricating film that eventually fragments, increasing the CoF. The CoF also increases with sliding distance, with values of 0.31, 0.33, and 0.38 at 1000m, 1500m, and 2000m, respectively, due to rising surface temperatures and frictional forces.

Fig. 7 Influence of load on coefficient of friction of Al2024 varying the speed and sliding distance

Factors affecting the CoF include the mechanical properties of the matrix material, the hardness and chemical stability of reinforcement particles, the matrix-reinforcement interfacial strength, and various tribological parameters.

4. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

The experiments aimed at investigating the influence of operating parameters on the tribological performance of the developed self-healing material were designed using the Taguchi Design of Experiments method. The objective was to determine the optimal operating parameters for enhancing the tribological performance of the material.

Table 1 lists the input parameters and their respective levels used for the experiments. An L9 Orthogonal array, as shown in Table 1, was constructed, and experiments were carried out for various combinations of these input parameters.

Two types of samples were tested: Pure Al2024 and Al6061+60Pb40Sn and the duration for each test was fixed at 1 hour.

Table 1 Input parameters for Design of experiment

Input parameters	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Load (N)	10	30	50
Speed (RPM)	300	600	900
Sliding distance (m)	1000	1500	2000

The experiments were conducted using a pin-on-disc tribometer to measure friction and wear volume. The experimental setup followed the L9 Orthogonal array design, and the friction and wear volume data obtained are summarized in Table 3. The results clearly indicate that the operating parameters have a significant impact on both contact friction and wear.

Table 2 L9 Orthogonal Array

Exp. No	Load	Speed	Sliding distance
1	10	300	1000
2	10	600	1500
3	10	900	2000
4	30	300	1500
5	30	600	2000
6	30	900	1000
7	50	300	2000
8	50	600	1000
9	50	900	1500

After recording the experimental data, a statistical analysis was performed to determine the Signal to Noise (S/N) ratio, which is a key metric for assessing wear behavior. The S/N ratio helps identify the optimal operating conditions by quantifying the variability of the results relative to the mean performance. This analysis is crucial for understanding the robustness of the material's wear performance under different operational settings.

Table 3 Tribo-performance test results

Exp.No	Sliding distance	Al2024		Al2024+PbSn		S/N ratio Al6061	S/N ratio Al2024 + PbSn
		COF (μ)	Weight loss (gms)	COF (μ)	Weightloss (gms)		
1	300	2.88	0.36	3.28	0.37	5.93	5.68
2	600	3.43	0.44	3.98	0.45	4.19	3.98
3	900	6.45	0.551	7.8	0.59	2.20	1.60
4	300	3.14	0.24	4.66	0.24	9.41	9.40
5	600	7.2	0.34	10.73	0.35	6.37	6.11
6	900	4.56	0.34	7.02	0.32	6.38	6.90
7	300	6.91	0.22	12.45	0.22	10.15	10.14
8	600	3.96	0.21	7.2	0.22	10.56	10.15
9	900	5.34	0.27	9.99	0.28	8.37	8.05

The statistical analysis of the S/N ratio revealed the significance of each operating parameter on the wear behavior of the samples. This information is valuable for optimizing the tribological performance of the developed self-healing material, providing insights into how to adjust operational settings for improved durability and efficiency.

Where n is the number of tests in a trial. The S/N ratios thus obtained for samples are given in Table 4. Subsequently the response for means was determined. The response for means of samples Al2024 and Al2024+PbSn are given in Table 5.7.

Table 4: Response for Means of test Samples for wear behavior

Sample	Level	Load	Speed	Sliding distance
Al2024	1	2.352	2.292	2.052
	2	2.637	2.597	2.143
	3	2.818	2.918	3.612
	Delta	0.466	0.627	1.560
	Rank	3	2	1
	% of contribution	17.57	23.63	58.80
Al2024+PbSn	1	2.745	3.537	3.068
	2	3.887	3.822	3.267
	3	5.060	4.333	5.357
	Delta	2.315	0.797	2.288
	Rank	1	3	2
	% of contribution	42.87	14.76	42.37

For a pure Al2024 sample, the analysis indicates that the percentage contribution of load to wear behavior is 17.57%, speed contributes 23.63%, and sliding distance accounts for 58.8%. In contrast, for the Al2024+ 60Pb40Sn sample, the load plays a more significant role, contributing 42.87%, with sliding distance at 42.37%, and speed contributing 14.76%.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

The regression analysis has been performed for all the materials in order to develop an empirical relation for the wear of the samples as a function of input parameters. The Empirical relation for wear in terms of load, speed and sliding distance for the materials tested are as follows.

Regression equation for Pure Al2024 sample

$$\text{Volume loss} = -1.71 + 0.0287 \text{ load} + 0.00190 \text{ Speed} + 0.003053 \text{ Sliding distance}$$

Regression equation for Pure Al2024+PbSn sample

$$\text{Volume loss} = -4.40 + 0.1215 \text{ load} + 0.00246 \text{ Speed} + 0.00449 \text{ Sliding distance}$$

Fig. 8 Surface plots

Based on the study conducted and the regression equations developed, Figure 9 illustrates the distribution of various operating parameters—namely load, speed, and sliding distance—on the wear behavior of the developed material. The figure highlights the prominent effects of sliding distance and load on wear.

For the pure Al2024 sample, the sliding distance is the dominant factor, contributing 59% to the wear. This indicates that the distance over which the material slides has a substantial impact on its wear rate. On the other hand, for the sample of Al2024 filled with solder material, load becomes the primary contributor, accounting for 43% of the wear. This suggests that the amount of force applied significantly influences the wear in this composite material.

The comparison within the figure demonstrates that both load and sliding distance are more critical than speed in determining the wear of the material. The data underscores the importance of controlling these two parameters to optimize the wear resistance of both pure and composite Al2024 samples. This insight is crucial for the design and application of these materials in environments where wear resistance is a key consideration.

Fig. 9 % contribution of operating parameters on wear behavior

Figures 10 present interaction plots for the Al2024 and Al2024+PbSn samples, showcasing how various interacting parameters impact their performance. These plots highlight the significant influence of load and sliding distance on the wear behavior of the materials. The analysis clearly shows that these two factors are the most critical in determining wear rates.

The interaction plots reveal a direct relationship between the wear rate and the load and sliding distance: as either parameter increases, the wear rate also rises. This suggests that higher loads and longer sliding distances exacerbate the wear on the materials, making them more susceptible to damage. The plots provide a visual representation of these trends, confirming that managing load and sliding distance is essential for optimizing the wear resistance of these samples.

for Al2024

for Al2024+PbSn

Fig. 10 Interaction plot

5. CONCLUSIONS

- The self-healing Al2024+PbSn alloy exhibits higher friction and wear compared to the pure Al2024 alloy composite.
- Tribological performance characteristics indicate that for the self-healing Al2024+PbSn alloy, contact friction decreases with increasing load but increases with rising speed. Additionally, wear escalates with both increased load and speed. The sliding distance significantly affects the coefficient of friction for the tested self-healing Al2024+PbSn alloy.
- The Taguchi design of experiments method has been utilized to analyze the wear performance of the self-healing Al2024+PbSn material under dry sliding conditions. The influence of operating parameters such as load, speed, and sliding distance was examined. Regression analysis was successfully applied to develop a relationship between material wear and operating parameters such as speed, load, and sliding distance.
- Regression analysis results indicate that load and sliding distance are significant factors for samples made with solder-filled Al2024, with load contributing 42% and sliding distance 43% to wear.
- Other parameters like speed also impact the tribological performance of the developed material. For samples made of pure Al2024 and Al2024+PbSn, speed contributes 23.6% and 17.5% to wear, respectively.

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